

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: British Geological Survey

Detecting Shallow Gas from
Marine Seismic Images

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1 Executive Summary

This data study group challenge focused on extracting information from legacy offshore seismic data. The British Geological Survey has an archive of thousands of images of scanned paper records that contain information about the marine subsurface, but these images are time-consuming to investigate manually. This challenge aimed to investigate methods to automatically extract information from these images, particularly identifying the presence of shallow gas below the seabed using patterns in the images. Shallow gas is a hazard that can threaten undersea cables, pipelines, and create problems for siting wind turbines. Knowing the location of hazardous gas will help to de-risk the installation of wind farms, a crucial infrastructure to achieve NetZero.

Seismic data allow geologists to identify different layers and structures below the seabed, including patterns that indicate shallow gas. Modern seismic data are recorded digitally, however in this challenge the data were images of paper records. The records consist of rolls of paper of varying lengths depending on the distance covered during the survey. The images of the records are of varying quality due to paper degradation.

In this DSG the team investigated whether machine learning approaches could be used to automatically detect shallow gas, using a small collection of hand-labelled images as training data. Another key question of interest was whether handwritten labels could be extracted that indicate the geographic location of the seismic records.

Enhancement of the images was investigated as a pre-processing step, including removing background, adjusting the spread of greyscale intensity, denoising and binarisation algorithms. Visually these approaches greatly improved the clarity of the signals in the images, with the choice of steps and parameters making a marked difference in the resulting similarity metrics.

The shallow gas detection was tackled using a multi-step deep learning approach. First, tiles were classified to identify the presence of gas within a tile. Next, an object detection algorithm highlighted the areas within the tile that demonstrated gas. Finally, a segmentation algorithm identified the pixels of shallow gas. Different algorithms were prototyped at each stage, with EfficientNet-B0 performing best for classification (85.88% accuracy) and object detection (12.80% intersection over union), and PSPNet performing best for image segmentation (99.53% accuracy). Binary images with wavelet denoising had the

best accuracy in the classification model when considering different pre-processing approaches.

Optical character recognition (OCR) models were compared to evaluate the success of identifying handwritten notes on the seismic records. These notes indicate the timings of the acoustic source, which can be cross referenced to a dataset with the acoustic source timings and geographic locations of the survey vessel at these times. This information allows for the images to be aligned in space. EasyOCR was the best performing OCR algorithm, with the original images performing better than preprocessed versions. Vertical lines on the images were identified using filters which both allowed for the vertical positions of the source timings to be found, and indicated the sections of the images that contained information rather than space.

The work in this DSG can be combined in future to create a pipeline that identifies shallow gas in seismic images and relates this to geographic coordinates. Future work includes further investigation and testing of the best performing algorithms, and a comprehensive evaluation of the effect of pre-processing on results. Different pre-processing pipelines performed best for the classification and OCR parts of this challenge, indicating that a one-size-fits-all approach to image preprocessing does not suit all downstream tasks.

2 Introduction

2.1 Background

The British Geological Survey (BGS) provides geoscience research and data, focussing on the responsible use of natural resources and resilience to environmental change and hazards. BGS holds large quantities of legacy data in both physical and digital form. Physical samples of rock core are held, as well as paper records of reports and surveys that were conducted before digital recording. The subsurface formed over millions of years, so whilst these records are tens of years old, they are still relevant and contain important information. These legacy records include the seabed seismic surveys used in this challenge.

Seismic surveys are conducted offshore using specialist vessels equipped with acoustic source(s) and receivers (Fig. 1). The acoustic source (types include airguns, boomers, and sparkers) is triggered and the reflections are recorded by the receivers. The subsurface contains different layers of material with different

Figure 1: Diagram showing a survey vessel towing a source and receiver array.

reflectance qualities, which means the seismic survey contains information about the subsurface without having to perform drilling operations. Experts can identify many features of the subsurface from seismic surveys, including the strata of rocks that make up the subsurface, and areas with shallow gas. Modern seismic surveys store data digitally; however, surveys conducted before the mid-nineties were generally only recorded on paper. Despite good storage conditions, the paper records began to deteriorate through age, so a digitisation programme was conducted to capture their information [11]. This digitisation converted the paper records to high-quality images for future use. The paper records were captured on rolls of paper of varying lengths depending on the distance travelled during the survey. This results in images that are far wider than their height, which are challenging to view on a computer screen.

These legacy seismic surveys can be studied to identify features of interest in the subsurface. Such investigations are carried out by trained experts and are time intensive. In this challenge, we are focusing on the presence of shallow gas below the seabed. Shallow gas presents a significant geotechnical hazard for offshore infrastructure, including wind turbines and other renewable energy developments. This study seeks to develop an automated, machine learning-based approach for detecting shallow gas within seismic images. This will enable a scalable and efficient analysis of legacy records to inform offshore planning and hazard assessment.

2.2 DSG Objectives

The overarching aim of the DSG is to work with the seismic survey images to automatically extract information. The two key questions of interest are:

- Can the pixels within the image be geolocated back to geographical coordinates?
- Can areas on the image that indicate shallow gas be automatically identified using patterns and features on the image?

The seismic scans contain reference lines and labels that indicate the position of the survey vessel when the acoustic sounder was deployed (shot points). The vertical line runs through the scan, and each is annotated with a corresponding reference of the form a/b where a refers to the line number (denoting the survey line reference) and b refers to the shot point. These labels can be cross-referenced with a dataset containing geographical coordinates. The labels may be handwritten or typeset.

The geographical alignment of the scans is crucial to be able to convert the shallow gas information from pixels to real locations.

The shallow gas hazard can be identified by an expert, but this is time-consuming and may be inconsistent across experts. An automatic method to identify gas would enable much higher throughput than human identification, allowing a much greater set of images to be analysed. Expert-labelled training data is available for some of the images which have identified shallow gas presence. Shallow gas comes in different forms, and different signatures (patterns shown on the scans) can signify its presence. These different features are not individually labelled on the mask images, instead, all are denoted as gas.

3 Data overview

3.1 Dataset description

The dataset utilised in this study comprises seismic reflection images generated from marine seismic surveys conducted between the 1960s and the 2000s. These historical records were manually scanned and stored as high-resolution JPEG2000 files. All images provided for the DSG were in JPEG format with a standardised height of 2725 pixels, though widths vary depending on the original survey line length. These datasets include 16 labelled images with binary masks indicating regions of shallow gas presence, as well as 92 unlabelled images.

An example image is shown in Fig. 2. This is one of the shorter records, with most images being wider than this example. The paper is not showing as white on this image, it is a grey tone. There is also an information card present on the image. This area of the image is not part of the seismic record, but is metadata about the survey. These features mean that pre-processing steps are important to detect the area of interest within the images.

We note that one of the images includes an associated mask that is 151 pixels wider horizontally. To align it with the corresponding image, 50 pixels were cropped from the left side and 101 pixels from the right.

3.2 Data quality

Following Mougan et al. [30] we evaluate the data quality:

16 labelled images. As the images were large (wide), they could be split into smaller images for algorithm training and testing, which mitigated the sufficiency issue of only having 16 labelled images.

4 Approach

4.1 Research Questions

To achieve the automated detection of shallow gas from seismic images, we address three key interconnected challenges: **image preprocessing**, **gas detection**, and the **extraction and georeferencing of handwritten labels**.

Our research is structured around the following key questions:

1. How can seismic images be effectively preprocessed to enhance machine learning (ML) performance while maintaining their geophysical integrity?

Legacy seismic images may vary in resolution, aspect ratio, and contrast due to differences in digitisation processes. Preprocessing aims to standardise these images with minimal or no distortion of their embedded seismic features. Carefully choosing preprocessing techniques, such as contrast enhancement, noise reduction, and rescaling, is important to optimise the quality of input data without distorting relevant seismic structures.

2. How can handwritten annotations be automatically extracted and georeferenced to align images with their real-world locations?

The seismic survey records contain information about the location of the reflection data, contained within vertical lines and reference labels (often handwritten). Automatically extracting and interpreting these labels requires the exploration of robust optical character recognition (OCR) and/or ML-based text recognition techniques to handle variations in handwriting styles, contrast levels, image distortions, and overlapping seismic traces. Integrating extracted labels with existing metadata allows for georeferencing, allowing seismic images to be spatially aligned with known survey routes. The feasibility of implementing these text detection methods is explored for label extraction.

3. What deep learning approaches are most effective for detecting gas

signatures?

The presence of shallow gas may be identified from distinctive attributes, such as acoustic blanking, bright spots, and velocity pull-down effects. This study examines the suitability of different neural network-based architectures to detect these features. For this, we will utilise the provided shallow gas masks that correspond with the seismic images.

5 Data preprocessing

5.1 Motivation

The legacy seismogram scans used in this study originated from paper records, which introduce several challenges for automated interpretation. Variability in recording techniques, ink artifacts, paper degradation, dust and water markings, as well as inconsistent contrast levels contribute to signal loss and noise in the data. These factors are particularly problematic when detecting shallow gas as gas accumulations can obscure underlying reflectors, reducing the visibility of critical geological features.

The dataset contains a mix of strong and faint seismic reflections, with gas-charged sediments often appearing as disrupted or attenuated waveforms. Conventional interpretation relies on visual assessment, which is subjective and affected by the limitations of historical records. Enhancing these images through preprocessing aims to mitigate non-geological artifacts and improve feature visibility without introducing distortions. This is particularly relevant for the detection of subtle gas-related anomalies, where improving signal clarity may aid in distinguishing true geological structures from imaging artifacts. By quantifying the effects of various processing techniques, this study assesses the feasibility of automated feature extraction and the impact of data conditioning on ML performance.

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Image processing workflow

An image processing method was developed to enhance seismic image quality while maintaining structural integrity. The workflow consisted of sequential preprocessing and postprocessing steps, each intended to target specific noise characteristics and contrast limitations present in the scanned legacy data.

The input image was loaded, then adaptive normalization was applied using Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) [32] to improve local contrast and highlight subtle seismic features. Background reduction followed to suppress low-frequency variations that may interfere with the visibility of seismic reflections. Denoising was performed using either a wavelet-based method or Non-Local Means (NLM) filtering, after which Otsu thresholding [31] was applied to generate a binarised image to emphasise structural features of interest. A schematic representation of the process is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the image processing workflow used in this study. Adaptive normalisation and contrast enhancement (CLAHE) were followed by an optional background reduction (subtraction) step, which was followed by one of two denoising methods. Otsu thresholding binarised images, after which outputs included the processed image, a binarised and processed image, a side by side comparison figure of the two images and similarity metrics for each image undergoing processing.

Processed images were saved along with their corresponding image fidelity metrics to assess their structural similarities to their source image. Before and after comparison figures were also generated to visually assess the processed output against the original image.

5.2.2 Adaptive normalisation

Adaptive normalisation was performed to enhance both global and local contrast in seismic images using the `cv2.normalize()` function [4]. Contrast stretching was applied by scaling pixel intensities relative to the mean image intensity (μ). A gain factor, $1 + \frac{128-\mu}{256}$, was used to adjust the contrast adaptively, compensating for variations in overall image brightness and improving contrast without over-amplifying noise. Pixel values were clipped to the range 0–255 to prevent saturation, preserving detail in both bright and dark regions.

Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalisation (CLAHE) [32] from the `cv2.createCLAHE()` function was then applied using two sets of parameters: the initial configuration with a clip limit of 0.75 (which controls the contrast enhancement strength) and a tile grid size of 16×16, followed by tests with a clip limit of 2.5 and a tile grid size of 8×8. A lower clip limit value reduces over-amplification of noise, while a higher value increases contrast.

5.2.3 Background removal

Background removal was performed to suppress large-scale intensity variations while preserving fine seismic features. A morphological mean filter with a disk radius of 100 pixels was applied to estimate the background and capture broad illumination trends without distorting local waveform details. Background removal was performed using a disk radius of 100 and a scaling factor of 0.8, where the scaling factor determines the strength of the background subtraction, effectively reducing the background interference without over-correcting the image. The background removal step was omitted from half the test runs to determine the resultant effect on final image fidelity, as background removal was the most computationally intensive procedure in the pipeline. This step was implemented using the `skimage.filters.rank.mean()` function from the `skimage` [42] package, in combination with a disk shape structuring element from `skimage.morphology`.

Following subtraction, pixel intensities were offset to ensure non-negativity, and values were clipped to the range 0–255 to maintain consistency with 8-bit image representation, enhancing contrast between seismic reflections and residual background noise.

5.2.4 Non-Local Means (NLM) denoising

For each processing run, either Non-Local Means (NLM) or wavelet-based denoising was applied. NLM denoising was applied to reduce random noise while maintaining seismic reflection continuity by exploiting non-local redundancy within the image. This method is commonly used for its ability to preserve fine details and structures in images, making it particularly well-suited for seismic data where continuity of the waveform lines is crucial.

The algorithm, implemented using OpenCV's `fastNlMeansDenoising()`, computes weighted averages of similar patches across the image, effectively suppressing noise without blurring structural features. Denoising was performed with varying parameter sets to assess performance. The initial configuration used a filtering strength (h) of 10 with a 7×7 template window and a 21×21 search window. The filtering strength determines how much noise is reduced, with higher values offering stronger noise suppression but potentially losing more detail. The template window size controls the local area around each pixel to compare, and the search window size defines the region across which similar patches are found. Additional tests were conducted with $h = 5$, a 9×9 template window, and a 31×31 search window to evaluate the trade-offs between noise reduction and detail preservation.

The NLM algorithm compared pixel neighbourhoods within the defined search window, assigning weights based on patch similarity to attenuate noise while preserving subtle geological features. NLM denoising demonstrated effective noise suppression while maintaining the integrity of seismic structures, providing complementary performance to wavelet-based approaches.

5.2.5 Wavelet denoising

Wavelet denoising was applied to suppress high-frequency noise while preserving essential seismic structures. The discrete wavelet transform (DWT) was employed to decompose the image into multiple frequency bands, facilitating targeted noise reduction. The Daubechies wavelets (db1 and db4) were selected due to their visual effectiveness in representing seismic waveforms with minimal distortion.

For each image, a multi-level decomposition was performed using `pywt.wavedec2()` [26]. Soft thresholding was applied to the wavelet coefficients using `pywt.threshold()` to selectively attenuate noise while maintaining structural integrity. The threshold values were set to 7 and 10 for db4

and db1, respectively, to balance noise reduction and feature preservation.

Following denoising, the image was reconstructed using the inverse wavelet transform (`pywt.waverec2()`). To mitigate artefacts introduced by wavelet decomposition, the reconstructed image was resized to match the original dimensions. This process ensured that noise was effectively reduced without altering the fundamental structural features of the seismic reflections.

Wavelet denoising was used to adaptively filter noise while retaining sharp transitions critical for seismic interpretation. However, care was taken to prevent excessive smoothing, which could obscure faint signals present in the original data.

5.2.6 Thresholding

Thresholding was performed to convert the processed grayscale images into binary format, facilitating the isolation of seismic waveforms from background artefacts. Otsu's method [31] was employed to determine an optimal global threshold by maximising inter-class variance between the foreground (signal) and background (noise). Otsu's method is a data-driven approach that automatically selects the threshold value based on the image histogram, aiming to retain image fidelity across varying contrast conditions. This method is implemented in the `threshold_otsu()` function from the `skimage.filters` package.

Pixels with intensities above the threshold were assigned a value of 255 (white), while those below were set to 0 (black), producing a binarised image. This step was critical for enhancing the visibility of seismic reflectors and suppressing residual background noise. Although binarisation inherently reduces grey-level information, it achieves clear feature delineation for downstream tasks involving machine learning-based analysis.

Process Step	Parameter Set A	Parameter Set B
Normalisation	alpha = 0 beta = 255	alpha = 0 beta = 255
Adaptive Contrast	clipLimit = 0.75 tileGridSize = (16, 16)	clipLimit = 2.5 tileGridSize = (8, 8)
Background Removal	disk_size = 100 scaling_factor = 0.8	disk_size = 40 scaling_factor = 0.7
Non-Local Means Denoising	h = 10 templateWindowSize = 7 searchWindowSize = 21	h = 10 templateWindowSize = 7 searchWindowSize = 21
Wavelet Denoising	wave type = db1 level = 1 threshold = 10	wave type = db4 level = 2 threshold = 7
Threshold	Otsu	Otsu

Table 1: Process settings for Parameter Sets A and B.

5.2.7 Image similarity metrics

To quantitatively assess the impact of image processing techniques on seismic reflection scans, a set of image integrity metrics was employed. These metrics evaluate structural similarity, noise levels, edge preservation, and the consistency of binary features. By applying these measures at different stages of processing, both pre- and post-thresholding, it was possible to monitor alterations in image quality and ensure the preservation of critical geological features. The metrics are: Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM), Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Edge Preservation Index (EPI), Intersection over Union (IoU) and Dice Coefficient. These metrics are described in detail in Appendix A.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Initial parameter selection and visual results

Initial parameter selections (Parameter Set A, Table 1) were set by visual inspection of processed images for clarity, contrast, and distinction of individual waveforms.

Metrics to assess the similarity of images were computed for each processing step prior to binarisation of images by Otsu thresholding. Additionally, similarity metrics were also computed to compare binarisations of original source images to binarisations of processed images.

Alterations in the visual presentation of images are presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. The intent of processing was to improve the readability of waveform data, enhancing weak waveforms while also minimising noise and artifacts. Colour and feature contributions from the paper and optical conditions have been reduced in Fig. 4, while contrast has been increased, resulting in an image with defined and separated waveforms, and better definition on faint and weak signals. In Fig. 5 non-signal artefacts have been suppressed, while contrast enhancement has improved waveform separation. Faint and low-amplitude signals are more distinguishable, facilitating a clearer interpretation of the scan.

Figure 4: Seismic reflection scan, 1968_3_19396513 in (a) its original state, (b) after processing with Parameter Set A, prior to Otsu thresholding, and (c) presented as a binary image.

A second set of parameters (Parameter Set B, Table 1) was chosen in an arbitrary fashion as a point of comparison. This secondary selection served to evaluate the impact of different parameter choices on waveform visibility and artifact suppression. By contrasting the results of Parameter Set A and Parameter Set B, the degree of variability introduced by parameter selection was assessed. Although both sets were selected without rigorous optimisation, differences in their performance provide insight into the sensitivity of the processing pipeline to input parameter variation.

Figure 5: Seismic reflection scan, 1998_RCK_19373397 shown in (a) its unprocessed state, (b) after processing with Parameter Set A, prior to Otsu thresholding, and (c) as a binarised output.

5.3.2 Image Similarity Metrics

Image similarity metrics were computed and compared after each processing step in the workflow in order to quantify the impact of normalisation, contrast enhancement, denoising, background subtraction, and thresholding on image fidelity. The results provide insight into how these preprocessing steps influence structural similarity, noise levels, and the preservation of geological features.

General Trends in Image Similarity Metrics

Table 2 shows that the computed metrics exhibit systematically higher similarity scores in non-background-subtracted images. Across all parameter sets, SSIM, PSNR, and EPI remained consistently higher for images without background subtraction, indicating that background removal introduced the most significant structural variations.

Effect of Normalisation and Contrast Enhancement

The Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) values following normalisation and adaptive contrast enhancement remained high across both parameter sets. The median SSIM was 0.968 for parameter set A and 0.844 for parameter set B. This indicates that normalisation and contrast enhancement had no measurable impact on similarity between the processed and reference images. A similar trend was

Image preprocessing	SSIM	PSNR	EPI
Normalisation and adaptive contrast			
A	0.968	27.0	0.997
B	0.844	18.0	0.952
Background subtraction			
A, background sub	0.321	3.9	0.997
B, background sub	0.378	4.7	0.952
Denoising			
A, background sub, NLM	0.028	4.4	0.761
A, no background sub, NLM	0.969	27.0	0.996
A, background sub, wavelet	0.028	4.4	0.761
A no background sub, wavelet	0.960	27.0	0.989
B, background sub, NLM	0.073	5.0	0.749
B, no background sub, NLM	0.875	18.0	0.949
B, background sub, wavelet	0.062	5.1	0.746
B no background sub, wavelet	0.873	18.1	0.947

Table 2: Median image similarity metrics (SSIM, PSNR, and EPI) for different processing configurations, comparing Non-Local Means (NLM) and Wavelet denoising with and without background subtraction

Image preprocessing	IoU	Dice
A, background sub, NLM	0.876	0.934
A, no background sub, NLM	0.970	0.985
A, background sub, wavelet	0.876	0.934
A no background sub, wavelet	0.970	0.985
B, background sub, NLM	0.929	0.963
B, no background sub, NLM	0.919	0.958
B, background sub, wavelet	0.931	0.964
B no background sub, wavelet	0.918	0.957

Table 3: Median image similarity metrics (IoU and Dice) on binary images with different processing configurations, comparing Non-Local Means (NLM) and Wavelet denoising with and without background subtraction

observed in the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Edge Preservation Index (EPI), where values were slightly lower for parameter set B. These results suggest that contrast enhancement preserved the fundamental structure of the images while not significantly altering the overall noise characteristics.

Effect of Background Subtraction

Background subtraction had the most pronounced impact on image similarity metrics, resulting in a significant reduction in both SSIM and PSNR. In background-subtracted images, the median SSIM dropped to 0.321 for parameter set A and 0.378 for parameter set B. A similar pattern is observed in PSNR where the value dropped, with parameter set A having a lower value than parameter set B.

These results indicate that background subtraction introduced substantial alterations to pixel intensities, particularly in regions containing faint reflectors. Despite these changes, EPI values remained stable. This suggests that while background subtraction had a pronounced effect on intensity-based metrics, it did not significantly alter structural features such as geological boundaries or waveform continuity.

Effect of Denoising

Denoising exhibited subtle differences in performance between NLM and wavelet filtering, with strong influence of the presence of background subtraction on the results. The SSIM and EPI metrics for the wavelet denoising are slightly lower than those for NLM, and slightly higher for PSNR and parameter set B. Denoising following background subtraction greatly reduces the SSIM and EPI metrics, whereas denoising without background subtraction results in small changes to the metrics.

Effect of Otsu Thresholding

Following Otsu thresholding, similarity metrics were computed to assess the extent to which key image features were preserved, shown in Table 3. The Intersection over Union (IoU) and Dice Coefficient values demonstrated a high degree of agreement between the thresholded images and their binarised reference counterparts, with median IoU ranging from 0.876 to 0.970 and Dice values between 0.934 and 0.985. These values indicate that, despite the transformations applied during preprocessing, the essential structural elements of the images were largely retained.

5.4 Discussion

These results indicate that the effects of image processing varied significantly depending on the operation applied. Normalisation and contrast enhancement variations tested had no measurable impact on similarity metrics or noise levels, confirming that these operations preserved the original structural integrity of the images. In contrast, background subtraction introduced the most significant changes, leading to a substantial reduction in SSIM and PSNR values while leaving edge structures largely intact, as evidenced by stable EPI scores.

The results of this image processing analysis indicate a need for a structured, data-driven approach to parameter selection in image preprocessing. While parameter choices in this study were based on heuristic assessment, their measurable impact on image similarity metrics, particularly in background subtraction and denoising, suggests that systematic optimisation could improve consistency and reproducibility. Future work should focus on developing an automated parameter tuning framework, employing techniques such as grid search, Bayesian optimisation, or genetic algorithms to refine parameter selection.

Further investigation into advanced denoising strategies, including deep learning-based approaches, may provide insight to the utility and optimisation of noise suppression methods while maintaining structural integrity. Ultimately, integrating an optimised preprocessing pipeline with a comprehensive evaluation of its impact on model performance will provide a clearer understanding of the trade-offs involved and ensure that parameter selection aligns with the intended application.

6 Detecting handwritten labels

6.1 Motivation

Georeferencing plays a critical role in the digitisation process of seismic data. Assigning real-world coordinates to the scanned images ensures that each data point can be accurately mapped to its original geographic location. This spatial referencing is vital for integrating the data with modern datasets, allowing for comprehensive temporal and spatial analyses of seismic activity. The georeferenced data within the provided images is embedded as vertical lines and text (often handwritten), which needs to be automatically extracted for further

Figure 6: Example image (horizontal slice) with vertical lines indicated using green bars above the image.

processing. In this section of the report, we document tests of ML-based approaches to identify and extract these handwritten annotations efficiently.

However, working with digital archives presents significant challenges as there is no standardised or consistently documented approach to processing and extracting text from historical handwritten materials. In this study, our objective is to explore a methodology that not only utilises multiple optical character recognition (OCR) techniques but also evaluates their effectiveness across different image sets, both original and preprocessed versions. Although time constraints limited our ability to test all possible methods comprehensively, this work serves as a proof-of-concept and lays the foundation for future research in optimising OCR pipelines for historical document analysis.

6.2 Vertical Grid lines detection

6.2.1 Motivation

The handwritten notes of interest are positioned adjacent to vertical grid lines in the background of the images, Fig. 6. Detecting these vertical lines will provide structural information about the images and enable georeferencing. More specifically, if the vertical lines can be accurately identified, we can reconstruct the underlying grid structure for each image. This reconstruction serves a dual purpose: first, it allows us to better understand the spatial distribution of handwriting within the image. Second, it enables a more targeted approach to data extraction.

Using the identified vertical grid lines, we can isolate the regions of the image

that contain handwritten information. Instead of processing the entire image, which may contain irrelevant background details, we can focus only on the relevant portions. This selective processing not only improves computational efficiency, but also improves the accuracy of handwriting recognition by reducing noise. Ultimately, this approach has the potential to significantly improve the automation of georeferenced data extraction, making the process more precise and scalable.

6.2.2 Methods

Vertical Line Extraction using Canny Edge Detection

To extract vertical lines within an image, we first apply the Canny edge detection algorithm [5] to crops of the original image. This multi-stage algorithm enhances important edge features while reducing noise. The process consists of several steps which work to find strong and interconnected edges within the image by smoothing the image and retaining high-intensity changes.

By applying the Canny edge detection algorithm, we obtain a refined set of edge features, which are then further processed to identify and extract the vertical lines present in the image. The Canny edge detection function in the OpenCV package [4] was used for this purpose.

Identifying Vertical Lines Using Hough Transform

To identify vertical lines, we use the Hough transform [14], a feature extraction technique designed to detect imperfect instances of objects with a particular shape through a voting procedure. The basic Hough transform is primarily used to detect straight lines from black-and-white images. One of its key advantages is its ability to tolerate gaps in feature boundaries while remaining relatively robust to image noise.

Using the `HoughLines()` function in the OpenCV package, lines with $-0.5 < \theta < 0.5$ degree angle between the x-axis and detected line are considered vertical lines. These lines are reconstructed into vertical grid lines by expanding them in the vertical direction so that they extend to the full image, not just the cropped section.

The aforementioned steps form the core of the vertical line construction process and are illustrated in Fig. 7. This method has been applied for multiple purposes: (1) automatically detecting and removing redundant parts of the original images, (2) reconstructing the grid structure in the background, and (3) automatically

Figure 7: The vertical line detection flowchart.

segmenting the images around the identified vertical lines, where handwritten text is often located. The details of these objectives are discussed in the following section.

6.2.3 Results

The vertical line detection procedure was applied to the binarised preprocessed images generated during the data preprocessing phase. These detected lines were then utilised for three primary objectives (Fig. 8).

The primary objective was to automatically detect and remove redundant sections of the original image. This was accomplished using a constructed grid image, a greyscale representation that contains only vertical lines (Fig. 9). In this grid, vertical lines are denoted in black. By identifying the column indices corresponding to white columns (those without vertical lines), we grouped consecutive white lines into blocks. Blocks with continuous vertical lines exceeding a predefined threshold were then cropped, effectively eliminating redundant areas from the original image.

It is important to note that this method does not specifically detect and crop the card section of the images but instead removes large sections of white blocks. In Fig. 10, portions of the card remain because some vertical lines were detected in this region, some of which correspond with vertical lines within the card information. Additionally, there is no universal threshold value that works for all images. Variations in image content may cause clusters of white blocks to appear in seismic signal regions, potentially leading to the unintentional removal of important information. Therefore, we recommend carefully selecting an appropriate threshold based on the specific characteristics of the image.

The second objective was to reconstruct the background grid lines. To achieve this, we applied the vertical line detection process to regions of the image where grid lines were most dominant, typically located at the top and bottom of the image. By

Figure 8: The general workflow used for image cropping, grid reconstruction, and slicing using vertical line (Vline) detection procedure.

focusing on these areas, we were able to reconstruct most of the grid lines.

Fig. 10 illustrates an example of the reconstructed grid lines, shown in red. It is important to note that we performed this reconstruction on cropped images obtained from the previous step. Although this step can be applied directly to the original image, we recommend using cropped images as they contain fewer redundant grid lines, making the reconstruction process more efficient and accurate.

The final objective was to slice the image into sections around the grid lines, creating a set of slices with grid lines and text. Using the x-axis coordinates of the background grid lines identified in the previous step, we define bounding boxes with a width of $[x - 100, x + 100]$ and an adjustable height. The image is then sliced around each x-coordinate, generating a list of segmented images. Figure 11 illustrates a set of slices derived from Fig. 10. In most investigated cases including this example, most slices contain handwriting; however, some may not include any handwriting or may capture non-relevant text due to imperfections in the detected grid lines.

In the next section we investigate methods to extract the characters from the labels. As this work was conducted concurrently during the DSG, the full images rather than extracted slices were used in the handwriting recognition work described

Figure 9: (a) The vertical lines identified in the image (b) the original image

Figure 10: Cropped image with identified grid lines which are overlaid onto the original image

Figure 11: Image slices around the identified grid lines

next.

6.3 Comparison of OCR methods for handwriting detection

6.3.1 Methods

Based on a literature review [15, 43, 44], we identified several OCR techniques suitable for handwriting detection. The following methods were considered:

- EasyOCR - a deep learning-based OCR library built on PyTorch, supporting over 80 languages and optimized for handwritten text recognition [24].
- PaddleOCR - a deep-learning-based package which is optimized for multilingual text recognition and angle correction [12].
- PyTesseract - a wrapper for Google's Tesseract-OCR engine, primarily used for printed text and known for its performance on high-resolution, high-contrast images [18].
- KerasOCR - a deep learning-based OCR method that integrates text detection and recognition into a single pipeline, improving the accuracy of structured text [13].
- Textractor - an AWS-based OCR service that utilizes cloud computing for text extraction, particularly effective for printed and structured text but also applicable to handwritten text [2].

6.3.2 Experimentation with OCR methods

We manually tested four of these OCR techniques on our dataset: EasyOCR, PaddleOCR, PyTesseract, and Textractor. In [15], authors state that one of the key benefits of PaddleOCR is its high accuracy, while EasyOCR also resulted in good performance. Each method was evaluated on original archival images to determine its baseline performance.

Our initial experiments showed that three of the four methods (EasyOCR, PaddleOCR, and Textractor) performed reasonably well, whereas PyTesseract performed poorly. This could be due to PyTesseract's reliance on high-quality, high-contrast images; archival scans often contain faded ink, noise, and uneven lighting, making it difficult for PyTesseract to extract accurate text.

We aim to extract handwritten coordinates and textual content from a dataset of images using EasyOCR and Textractor libraries to benchmark the models.

To effectively process high-resolution images, a slicing approach was employed. Each image was divided horizontally into smaller, manageable chunks of width 500 pixels to ensure that the OCR tools could handle the data without being overwhelmed by the full-resolution image. A classification dataset was created from the sliced images. Each slice was manually classified into one of two categories: "text" (images that contain any form of textual content), or "no text".

This dataset served as the ground truth for generating confusion matrices, thereby providing a robust basis for comparing the classification performance of both OCR tools.

To evaluate their performance, confusion matrices were generated for both OCR methods, Fig. 12. These matrices compare the OCR outputs against the manually classified ground truth data, providing detailed insights into error rates and detection accuracy. Both OCR tools were assessed on the basis of accuracy. EasyOCR exhibited a higher sensitivity in recognizing complex handwritten annotations, whereas Textractor demonstrated robust performance in detecting structured printed text. EasyOCR demonstrates better performance across the 47 slices with text and 45 slices without text in the test set.

As part of this investigation of the results of the two models were saved as JSON files containing the detected text in the images. This process can then be used as part of an image processing pipeline.

Figure 12: Confusion matrices for EasyOCR and Textractor models applied to slices of seismic images

6.3.3 Further testing of EasyOCR

Given that EasyOCR outperformed other methods in initial analysis, we decided to proceed with EasyOCR for further testing to investigate performance improvements.

To further analyse the impact of different preprocessing techniques, the next section provides a detailed examination of EasyOCR’s performance using one image across various processed versions and the original, highlighting how different preprocessing approaches influenced recognition accuracy.

Since handwritten labels are found on the top of the image in some and on the bottom in others, we sliced the image horizontally, extracting 20% of the top and bottom areas of the image, then rejoined the slices, and further sliced vertically to give a slice of width 500 pixels. This allowed us to accommodate for the position of the handwritten labels. For more recognizable input, we rotated the sliced images 90 degrees clockwise to that the text was aligned horizontally.

In general, the processed images perform better than the binaries in all sets according to a qualitative visual comparison. The no background subtraction and non-local means normalisation that denoise the processed image ‘No_BG_Subtract_nLMeans_processed_img’ performed better than all other preprocessed versions (2 out of 13 labels extracted accurately). However, the original performs the best of all (4 out of 13 extracted correctly as well as more accurate recognition in images where text was not extracted 100% accurately).

Example slices and their detected text are found in Fig. 13 and 14. However, EasyOCR performed on both the best preprocessed version and the original indicated almost fully accurately whether the image does or does not contain text.

Figure 13: EasyOCR results for slice 12. (a) Original image, “95/5” detected, (b) Best performing processed (NoBGSnLM) image, “%5/5” detected

Figure 14: EasyOCR results for slice 6. (a) Original image, “95/2” detected, (b) Best performing processed (NoBGSnLM) image, “95/” detected

6.4 Discussion

This work has shown partial success with identifying the grid lines on the seismic images and identifying handwritten labels. In particular, EasyOCR showed promise for extraction of labels. EasyOCR’s performance on detecting labels was almost completely accurate, but the extraction of handwritten labels only found 4/13 correctly using the best-performing input images. Our literature review found that EasyOCR is well-suited for recognizing handwritten text in archival

images, which are similar to our dataset [6]. Several studies have highlighted Tesseract's limitations when processing low-quality images, which aligns with its poor performance in our testing (generally not detecting text or inaccurately extracting text). For instance, in [16] authors demonstrate that low-resolution inputs negatively affect OCR accuracy, proposing a cascaded network to enhance image resolution and improve recognition. [33] discusses how document artifacts and noise further degrade Tesseract's performance, advocating for a neural-based preprocessor to address such issues. Studies have shown that Tesseract performs well only under ideal conditions, such as noise-free, single-column text in a clear printed font, but struggles with degraded or handwritten documents [25]. For example, [20] found that general OCR processors like Tesseract delivered near-perfect results only in controlled settings, while Textractor demonstrated higher accuracy across various noise types and languages.

For this study group, we did not have a labelled OCR dataset, and due to the nature of OCR investigations, much of our investigation was qualitative. Ideally, a more quantitative comparison would have been performed and presented across the four tested models similar to that presented for EasyOCR and Textractor, the lack of this result is a key limitation of this section. Further processing of the OCR output could be considered for future work, such as manipulating the detected output into the expected format. For example, a percentage sign was often detected in the place of the forward slash, and letters were detected in place of numbers. In these cases, an additional processing step that took the second most probable character from the OCR output could be employed, or other adaption methods to improve results for the practical application.

As the work was performed by multiple groups simultaneously during the DSG, it was not possible to perform the handwriting detection work after the slices were detected following the grid line detection described earlier in this section. Putting these parts of the work together would enable the extracted handwriting to be linked with its associated vertical line, and the handwritten label applied to this line. In addition, further investigation of the preprocessing steps and the difference these make to label detection could be investigated over a wider range of input images. It is surprising that processing that visually improves the clarity of handwritten labels does not translate to an improvement in finding them using EasyOCR.

The motivation for exploring handwriting detection was to enable automatic geographical alignment of the seismic survey images. This is so that features

within the images can be connected to real space rather than pixel space. In the next section we explore the third research question: identifying shallow gas within the images. If the work of this section and the next section can be successfully automated, then shallow gas can be identified on the seismic images, and also located in geographical coordinates.

7 Shallow gas detection

7.1 Motivation

Seismic interpretation plays a critical role in understanding the subsurface, particularly in detecting shallow gas accumulations under the seabed that pose risks to existing and new infrastructure. Traditional seismic analysis relies on expert-driven interpretation, which is time-consuming and subject to human bias. Advances in ML, particularly in computer vision, offer an opportunity to automate and enhance this process. By leveraging deep learning models, we aim to develop a robust multi-stage methodology for detecting and characterising shallow gas features in seismic imagery using the provided annotated images.

7.2 Methods

We formulate our problem as a multi-stage deep learning pipeline that includes three key computer vision tasks: classification, object detection, and segmentation, as illustrated in Fig. 15.

Classification provides an initial large-scale filtering mechanism, distinguishing between gas-bearing and non-gas-bearing tiles. Object detection further localises gas features within individual sub-sections, while segmentation delineates their precise boundaries and offers a detailed mapping of gas deposits.

Given the limited availability of labelled data and class imbalance (a small proportion of pixels within the images correspond to gas), we employ data augmentation techniques and transfer learning to improve model generalisation.

Figure 15: Deep learning pipeline developed to obtain predictions of shallow gas in seismic scans

7.2.1 Data preparation

As this work was performed concurrently with the work on image pre-processing the images were not processed according to the findings of the pre-processing section.

Tiling Although the heights of the records have all been set to 2725 pixels, there is considerable variation in their widths. To train our data across different models, the images and their corresponding annotation masks were systematically divided into smaller, uniform tiles. Standardising our input dimensions enables efficient batch processing in deep learning models. Each image was vertically sliced into non-overlapping tiles of size 500×2725 pixels from left to right (as shown in Fig. 16), ending tile that did not suffice 500px in width was discarded. Tiling produced 562 tiles, 150 containing gas and 412 without gas.

Figure 16: Example of tiling a record (2008-2-line15.jpeg) into 2725x500 slices.

The dataset was then randomly split into training (70%), validation (15%), and

test (15%) sets. All classification data are tiled in the same manner.

Gas mask coordinate extraction The coordinate data is used for object detection. Bounding box coordinates (X-max, X-min, Y-max, Y-min as shown in Fig. 17) were extracted for each mask segment and recorded in a structured format, allowing seamless integration with ML models or other analytical workflows.

Figure 17: Illustration of coordinate extraction of an area of gas within the mask images

Gas mask region cropping This dataset consists of zoomed-in images based on coordinates obtained from the gas mask coordinate extraction process. The images and masks are loaded, and the corresponding bounding box coordinates are used for cropping. Each image is cropped according to these coordinates, aligning it precisely with its corresponding mask. The cropped images and masks are then systematically stored in an organised directory for further analysis. This structured approach facilitates the precise localisation of regions of interest, enhancing applications such as object detection and ML.

7.3 Classification

The classification task aims to differentiate seismic tiles based on the presence or absence of shallow gas. Given the complex and high-dimensional nature of seismic imagery, deep learning models were employed to learn robust feature representations. A range of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) were benchmarked for their ability to extract spatial patterns indicative of gas presence. These models were implemented primarily in PyTorch, leveraging its flexibility for deep learning research and fine-tuning.

7.3.1 Models

We benchmarked several models for binary classification of seismic tiles:

- ResNet-18 [19]: A deep CNN with 18 layers and residual connections that help mitigate vanishing gradients, allowing for deeper networks to train effectively. It was chosen for its strong baseline performance and efficient feature extraction.
- DenseNet-121 [21]: A densely connected CNN where each layer is connected to every other layer, reducing redundancy and improving gradient flow. It was included for its parameter efficiency and ability to reuse learned features, which can be beneficial for limited seismic data.
- MobileNetV2 [35]: A lightweight CNN optimized for mobile applications, using depthwise separable convolutions to reduce computational cost. It was selected to evaluate whether a compact model could achieve competitive performance while being computationally efficient.
- EfficientNet-B0 [40]: A CNN that adopts a compound scaling method to optimize depth, width, and resolution in a balanced manner. It was chosen due to its strong accuracy-to-efficiency ratio, making it one of the most effective models for image classification tasks.
- MLP-Mixer [41]: A fully multi-layer perceptron-based architecture that does not rely on convolutions or self-attention but instead processes images by mixing information across patches. It was included to explore non-convolutional architectures and assess their effectiveness in seismic classification tasks.

In general, choosing neural networks with residual connectivity (e.g. ResNet) and automatic search capability (e.g. EfficientNet) gives better results as benchmarked in [48]. The MLP-Mixer has demonstrated competitive performance in image classification tasks [41], and was included in our benchmarks following the paper [10], where an MLP-Mixer was deployed to classify gas regions in seismic images.

Each model was initialised with ImageNet-pretrained weights and fine-tuned on the seismic images. An additional classification head was appended to each pre-trained model, consisting of a dense layer (128 neurons, ReLU activation), a dropout layer (rate 0.5), and a final dense layer (1 neuron, sigmoid activation). This classification block was uniformly applied across all models to standardize the output structure and ensure comparability in performance, as outlined in Table 4.

The input seismic tiles were resized to 224×224 pixels, which involved altering

Layer	Configuration
Pre-trained Model	n channels
Dropout	0.3
Dense	(n, 1)

Table 4: Classification block for gas region detection models.

the aspect ratio from the original 2725×500 rectangular format. This resizing was necessary for compatibility with standard CNN architectures but may have introduced some spatial distortions. The images were then normalised with a mean of 0.5 and a standard deviation of 0.5. The models were trained using the Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss function and optimised with Adam (lr = 0.0001). Training was conducted for 10 epochs with early stopping based on validation loss.

The MLP-Mixer model was set up with a slightly different architecture compared to the CNN-based models. The seismic images were first converted into patches using a patch size of 16×16 , which divides the image into smaller regions for feature extraction. The model aggregates features from all patches using adaptive average pooling and classifies the tiles into gas/non-gas categories using a final linear layer with two output units. The MLP-Mixer model was optimized using Adam (lr = 0.001) and trained for 20 epochs with early stopping based on cross-entropy loss.

7.3.2 Fine-tuning

Deep learning models often require fine-tuning to optimise performance, especially in specialised tasks with limited training data. Fine-tuning involves modifying various aspects of the training process to improve accuracy, generalisation, and robustness. In this study, several fine-tuning strategies were employed, including oversampling, focal loss, dropout, learning rate scheduling, and threshold tuning. These techniques were chosen to address specific challenges such as class imbalance, model overfitting, and decision-boundary optimisation.

Oversampling was used to increase the representation of gas within the training phase, using `ImbalancedDatasetSampler` from the `torchsampler` package. This should help prevent the model from favouring the majority class and improve

generalisation of the model. Focal loss [27] was also used as a strategy to improve the performance for gas presence, a modification of cross-entropy loss which weights for class imbalance and emphasises examples that are more difficult.

Dropout [37] is a regularisation technique that was used to help reduce overfitting within the network, particularly important with a modest size training dataset. The ReduceLROnPlateau (RoP) scheduler adjusts the learning rate based on validation loss stagnation. This helps the model to continue improving rather than training with little validation loss change. Threshold tuning is used to tailor the outputs so that the balance between false positives and false negatives can be optimised.

7.3.3 Contrastive learning

Contrastive learning [8] is a self-supervised learning technique that learns feature representations by maximising the similarity between different augmented views of the same image while minimising the similarity between different images. This is particularly useful when working with limited labelled images where additional unlabelled images are available, such as in this DSG.

In this study, contrastive learning was implemented using EfficientNet-B0 as the encoder, where the final classification layer was removed and replaced with a projection head to map high-dimensional features into a lower-dimensional representation space. The framework consisted of the following steps:

Semi-supervised learning

Semi-supervised learning [7] consists of both unsupervised learning and supervised learning. Unsupervised learning is used to create meaningful representations by exploiting the available unlabelled data. Strong data augmentations were applied to unlabelled seismic images.

The contrastive transform pipeline is used to create meaningful representations by exploiting the available unlabelled data (tiled in the same manner as the annotated data), and applying strong data augmentations to unlabelled seismic images. Each image is transformed into two different augmented versions using random resizing, cropping, and greyscale conversion, ensuring that the network learns invariant features regardless of these transformations.

The process begins with resizing the image to 300×300 pixels using `transforms.Resize`, followed by `transforms.RandomResizedCrop`, which randomly crops a portion of the image within a scale range of 80% to 100% of

the original size, introducing variation in object positioning. `transforms.RandomHorizontalFlip` is applied to randomly flip the image, enhancing diversity. Additionally, `transforms.ColorJitter` adjusts brightness, contrast, saturation, and hue within specified ranges, while `transforms.RandomGrayscale` converts the image to grayscale with a 20% probability, simulating different lighting conditions. The transformed images are then converted to tensor format with `transforms.ToTensor`, and pixel values are standardised using `transforms.Normalize` with a mean of [0.485, 0.456, 0.406] and a standard deviation of [0.229, 0.224, 0.225], commonly used in pre-trained models like ResNet. These augmentations enhance the model’s ability to learn robust and invariant representations from seismic images, improving generalisation in downstream tasks.

The Normalised Temperature-scaled Cross-Entropy Loss (NT-Xent) [8] was used to optimise the encoder. Given two augmented versions of an image, z_1 and z_2 , their cosine similarity was computed:

$$\text{sim}(z_i, z_j) = \frac{z_i \cdot z_j}{\|z_i\| \|z_j\|}, \quad (1)$$

where z_i and z_j are L_2 -normalised feature embeddings. The loss is weighted to bring the similarity of augmented versions of the same image closer together, and push apart different images.

EfficientNet-B0 Encoder and Projection Head

The encoder was initialised with EfficientNet-B0 pre-trained weights from the unsupervised contrastive learning model. The classifier head was removed, and a projection head consisting of two fully connected layers with ReLU activation was added. This transformation helped map feature embeddings into a space suitable for contrastive learning.

Training Process

The model was trained using the Adam optimiser with a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} for 10 epochs. The batch size was set to 32. The learned feature representations were later transferred to a supervised classification model by reusing the trained encoder weights.

Supervised Fine-tuning

After contrastive pretraining, the encoder weights were transferred to a supervised

binary classification model to predict gas presence. The new model was fine-tuned using a focal loss function to handle class imbalance. The approaches and parameters are the same as the pre-trained encoder weights, leading to accelerated convergence and improved performance compared to training from scratch.

7.4 Object detection

The model designed for object detection uses an EfficientNet-B0 backbone to predict bounding box coordinates for target objects in seismic images. We applied a transformation pipeline that resizes images to 640×640 , converts them to tensors, and normalises pixel values to improve training stability. A custom dataset class is implemented to load images and extract bounding box coordinates, which are normalised based on the original image dimensions. The dataset is then split into training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) subsets.

The model architecture consists of an EfficientNet-B0 feature extractor, pre-trained on ImageNet, where the classification head is replaced with a custom regression head predicting bounding box coordinates $[x_{\text{center}}, y_{\text{center}}, \text{width}, \text{height}]$. The extracted feature maps pass through an adaptive average pooling layer before being flattened and fed into fully connected layers. The training process leverages the Adam optimiser with a learning rate of 0.0001 and the SmoothL1 loss function to handle regression-based predictions. A learning rate scheduler (`ReduceLRonPlateau`) is incorporated to adjust the learning rate dynamically based on validation loss, reducing it when performance stagnates. The training loop spans 50 epochs, tracking both training and validation losses while updating model parameters. The model aims to learn robust representations from seismic images, ensuring accurate object localisation despite variations introduced by data augmentation and transformation.

7.5 Image segmentation

In the segmentation benchmark step, we aimed to develop robust models capable of accurately delimiting regions containing shallow gas. To achieve this, we experimented with various segmentation models well-known in the literature and relevant to seismic facies detection [1, 9, 46, 50]. The benchmarking process leveraged the segmentation models library [22], facilitating a comprehensive comparison of different architectures [29].

Consistent with established practices in semantic segmentation, we utilized U-

Net, FPN, PSPNet, and SegFormer architectures in our experiments [3, 1]. These architectures were selected based on their relevance and performance in tasks requiring detailed spatial understanding. Their descriptions and contributions to our study are outlined below:

- U-Net [34]: A widely-used fully convolutional network developed for biomedical image segmentation. It features an encoder-decoder architecture with skip connections that preserve spatial information, making it effective for segmenting small and irregularly shaped objects, such as seismic gas regions.
- Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) [28]: A multi-scale feature aggregation framework designed for object detection and segmentation. It creates a top-down pathway with lateral connections, enhancing the network’s ability to detect objects at varying scales, particularly in seismic data with multi-scale gas formations.
- Pyramid Scene Parsing Network (PSPNet) [49]: A segmentation model that employs a pyramid pooling module to capture global context and improve scene understanding. Its ability to aggregate multi-scale contextual information makes it particularly suited for identifying horizontal gas areas in seismic images.
- SegFormer [47]: A transformer-based segmentation model that combines hierarchical feature extraction with lightweight MLP decoders. Its robust global context modeling and efficiency make it an ideal candidate for high-resolution seismic segmentation tasks.

Each model was trained on 224×224 image patches, paired with their respective binary masks. We utilized ResNet-50 as the encoder backbone with pre-trained weights from ImageNet for feature extraction. The training process was conducted with a batch size of 32 for 20 epochs. The optimization strategy involved the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 and a weight decay of the same value. The loss function employed was the Dice Loss, which is particularly suitable for handling class imbalance in binary segmentation tasks.

The loss encourages precise segmentation while being robust to class imbalance [38].

7.6 Results

Validation accuracy, validation loss, and threshold optimisation were used to evaluate the models’ performance. The models were also compared based on their sensitivity, specificity, and AUC across varying thresholds.

7.6.1 Classification

Benchmark results are shown in Table 5. The best-performing model was EfficientNet-B0, but all models achieved an accuracy of over 75%.

Model	Accuracy (%)	AUC (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
ResNet-18	77.65	77.42	54.55	85.71
DenseNet-121	76.47	74.96	50.00	85.71
MobileNetV2	75.29	68.98	45.45	85.71
EfficientNet-B0	80.00	82.83	63.64	85.71
MLP-Mixer	77.65	-	68.42	80.30

Table 5: Performance metrics of the models for gas region classification.

With the knowledge gained from baseline models, the EfficientNet-B0 model with pre-trained weights from ImageNet was selected for further fine-tuning using oversampling, focal loss, dropout, RoP and threshold tuning.

We explore the impact of these adjustments across models, including ResNet34, ResNet50, EfficientNet-B1, EfficientNet-B0, and MLP-Mixer, and summarised the top-performing strategies in Table 6. Among the models tested, EfficientNet-B0 not only outperformed others in terms of accuracy (85.88%), AUC (89.31%), sensitivity (57.69%), and specificity (98.31%) for the 70 epoch version, but also showed superior performance in balancing accuracy with computational efficiency.

To further improve accuracy and data balance, contrastive learning was introduced using an EfficientNet-B0 backbone. Unlike the traditional classification-based EfficientNet-B0 model, the contrastive learning approach leveraged a self-supervised learning framework where representations were learned by maximising similarities between positive pairs and minimising similarities between negative pairs. This resulted in improved feature extraction

Model	Acc. (%)	AUC (%)	Sens. (%)	Spec. (%)
ResNet34 - No oversampling	78.82	81.90	41.67	93.44
ResNet34	82.35	83.56	52.38	92.19
ResNet34 - Dropout 0.3	84.71	86.11	73.08	89.83
ResNet34 - Dropout 0.5	78.82	79.93	47.06	86.76
EfficientNet B1	77.65	84.99	50.00	87.30
EfficientNet B1 - Dropout 0.3	81.18	86.76	71.43	84.83
EfficientNet B3 - Dropout 0.5	75.29	80.94	16.67	98.36
EfficientNet B0	80.00	83.54	58.33	88.52
EfficientNet B0 - 70 Epochs	85.88	89.31	57.69	98.31
EfficientNet B0 - Adjusted Threshold 0.005, Dropout 0.3, 70 Epochs	82.35	89.31	76.92	84.75
Contrastive Learning - ResNet34, Dropout 0.3	71.76	70.67	68.00	73.33
Contrastive Learning - EfficientNet B0, Dropout 0.3	82.35	75.74	64.71	86.76
Contrastive Learning - EfficientNet B0, Dropout 0.3, Threshold 0.47	84.71	83.82	82.35	85.29

Table 6: Performance comparison of differently fine-tuned models (accuracy, AUC, sensitivity and specificity). Focal loss, RoP and Oversampling are omitted in the table but applied throughout on all fine-tuned models, unless otherwise mentioned the models are run for 50 epochs

Figure 18: Threshold changes with contrastive learning and EfficientNet-B0

and model robustness. This model achieved an accuracy of 84.71%, AUC of 83.82%, sensitivity of 82.35%, and specificity of 85.29%.

The Contrastive Learning model and EfficientNet-B0 differ in how they balance sensitivity (recall) and specificity across classification thresholds. The contrastive model shows a clear crossover in Fig. 18, where sensitivity starts at 1.0 and declines sharply while specificity rises. This indicates high threshold sensitivity, meaning it detects more true positives at lower thresholds but at the cost of more false positives. Its reliance on feature separation rather than absolute classification confidence makes threshold tuning essential for optimal performance. However, with further training and larger-scale contrastive pre-training, the model could learn more discriminative features, potentially improving its stability and generalisation.

In contrast, EfficientNet-B0 maintains a stable trade-off in Fig. 18, with no crossover and both metrics starting high (0.75-0.80). This suggests it is less dependent on threshold adjustments, providing consistent performance with a balanced false positive and false negative rate.

If maximising recall is the priority, the contrastive model is useful but requires careful tuning and could benefit from further training on larger datasets. However, for robust, well-balanced performance, EfficientNet-B0 is the better choice as it preserves both specificity and recall across thresholds with minimal adjustments.

7.6.2 Object detection

EfficientNet-B0, initialised with pre-trained weights from ImageNet and trained with ReduceOnPlateau (RoP) for coordinate prediction, was selected due to its effectiveness in extracting features from seismic image data during the previous classification step. EfficientNet-B0 is a CNN optimised for high accuracy and efficiency, originally designed for image classification but adapted here for object detection by predicting bounding box coordinates around the gas mask within image tiles. The input images used for training were extracted seismic tiles containing various features, including gas mask regions and corresponding masks to guide the learning process.

The object detection task involves identifying regions of interest by predicting bounding box coordinates which localises the gas mask within each image tile. The model's performance was evaluated using the following metrics: Mean Intersection over Union (IoU) of 12.80%, Mean Center Distance Error of 26.14%, Mean Width Error of 21.71%, and Mean Height Error of 2.93%. The formulae for these metrics are outlined in Appendix B.

Qualitative observations suggest that larger mask regions were more accurately predicted. However, smaller gas regions were more challenging to localise, particularly when they spanned multiple image tiles (eg Fig. 19b). The low MHE indicates the model's ability to predict the depth of gas regions accurately, although the low IoU indicates that these regions are not well aligned with the true masks. Further work, such as implementing tiling strategies with overlap, and using deeper architectures like EfficientNet-B1, may improve detection performance.

7.6.3 Image segmentation

For the segmentation task, we use the input data described in Section 7.2.1 with no additional transformations to the original images. For the masks we invert the binary classifications (this means that the targets for modelling are 0s instead of 1s).

Table 7 summarises the results of the segmentation benchmark, where the models were evaluated on accuracy, intersection over union (IoU), Dice coefficient, AUC, sensitivity (recall), and specificity on a test set. PSPNet achieved the highest IoU and Dice Coefficient, indicating superior segmentation performance, Fig. 20 shows a comparison between an input and its predicted gas mask.

Figure 19: Preliminary object detection result visualisation. Each image is a different section from the seismic images, with the ground truth of the shallow gas denoted in green and the EfficientNet-B0 bounding box denoted in red.

Figure 20: An example image, predicted and ground truth mask using PSPNet.

The SegFormer model also demonstrated competitive results, particularly in sensitivity, making it a strong candidate for detecting smaller gas regions, supporting the findings of [46].

Model	Acc. (%)	IoU (%)	Dice (%)	AUC (%)	Sens. (%)	Spec. (%)
U-Net	94.85	27.94	43.68	97.66	93.41	94.87
FPN	99.34	59.64	74.72	88.20	71.90	99.69
PSPNet	99.53	62.64	77.03	94.53	79.86	99.78
SegFormer	99.24	60.63	75.49	93.68	81.24	99.47

Table 7: Performance metrics of models for gas region segmentation. Metrics are Accuracy, IoU, Dice score, AUC, Sensitivity, and Specificity.

For the segmentation task, we also compared with a U-Net model and images cropped using the results from the object detection step using coordinate prediction (see example prediction in Fig. 21). Comparison between U-Net models using initial true bounding box images (A) and the images cropped using coordinates derived from object detection (B) show improvement in IoU and Dice score, but a reduction in accuracy (see Table 8). These changes could be a result of the increase in proportion of gas pixels within the cropped images compared to the full images leading to better identification of the gas and potentially an over prediction of gas (which could correspond with lower accuracy scores). The PSPNet model, the best performing model with the initial extracted images (Table 7) was not tested for the cropped images, however this is recommended for future investigation.

Figure 22 demonstrates the workflow by presenting an example of an input seismic

Figure 21: The U-Net (B) example with input images produced by cropping procedure using coordinates predicted by objected detection model. The predicted mask left unscaled to initial aspect image size.

image, the predicted segmentation mask, the ground truth mask, and an overlay. The overlay highlights the agreement between the model’s prediction and the actual data, with red indicating predicted regions and green representing ground truth annotations.

Model	Accuracy (%)	IoU (%)	Dice (%)
U-Net (A)	94.85	27.94	43.68
U-Net (B)	69.07	72.37	58.18
PSPNet	99.53	62.64	77.03

Table 8: Performance metrics comparison between U-Net segmentation models with initial extracted images (A) and with images cropped using object detection coordinates (B); PSPNet model from Table 7) shown for reference.

7.6.4 Image quality processing

A pipeline was developed to test different image preprocessing methods on ML shallow gas classification performance. For this test, the EfficientNet-B0 classification model was used with all fine tuning processes. For each entry in Table 9, the model is trained on different sets of processed images to evaluate how the preprocessing steps alter the ML performance.

Figure 22: Illustration of the classification-segmentation pipeline applied to seismic data. The input image is first classified for gas presence, and if detected, the segmentation model predicts the regions of interest. The overlay shows the alignment between the predicted mask (red) and the ground truth mask (green).

The original images do not feature as the highest scoring image set for any of the metrics. Several versions of the binary images show an increase in performance on several metrics, with the binary images, parameter set B with wavelet normalisation having the highest accuracy (91%) which is an 11% improvement on the value for the original image set. This experiment shows that performance improvement in the ML tasks can be generated using image preprocessing techniques on the input data.

7.7 Discussion

The classification results indicate that EfficientNet-B0 baseline model with oversampling and focal loss, trained for 70 epochs, performed the best in predicting shallow gas using a classical supervised learning strategy, achieving the highest AUC (89.31%) and a well-balanced sensitivity-specificity trade-off. This superior performance can be attributed to EfficientNet's efficient feature extraction, the oversampling strategy mitigating class imbalance, and focal loss

Image Quality Processing	Acc.	AUC	Sens.	Spec.
Parameter Set A, Wavelet Norm., No Background Subtraction - Binary Images	89%	91%	81%	93%
Parameter Set A, nL Means Norm., No Background Subtraction - Binary Images	88%	94%	85%	89%
Parameter Set B, Wavelet Norm., No Background Subtraction - Binary Images	91%	94%	74%	95%
Parameter Set B, nL Means Norm., No Background Subtraction - Binary Images	88%	96%	69%	97%
Parameter Set B, nL Means Norm., Background Subtraction - Binary Images	86%	91%	62%	97%
Parameter Set B, Wavelet Norm., Background Subtraction - Greyscale	85%	88%	67%	92%
Parameter Set A, Wavelet Norm., No Background Subtraction - Greyscale	79%	89%	64%	84%
Parameter Set B, nL Means Norm., Background Subtraction - Greyscale	84%	86%	68%	89%
Parameter Set B, nL Means Norm., No Background Subtraction - Greyscale	82%	88%	64%	89%
Parameter Set A, nL Means Norm., No Background Subtraction - Greyscale	79%	92%	76%	79%
Parameter Set B, Wavelet Norm., No Background Subtraction - Greyscale	80%	90%	65%	86%
Parameter Set B, Wavelet Norm., Background Subtraction - Binary Images	79%	80%	60%	87%
Parameter Set A, nL Means Norm., Background Subtraction - Binary Images	86%	89%	69%	93%
Original Images	80%	84%	58%	89%

Table 9: Performance Comparison of Different Image Quality Processing Methods

improving learning from difficult cases. On top of that, contrastive learning with EfficientNet-B0 at a specific classification threshold of 0.47, combined with oversampling and focal loss, also demonstrated strong performance (AUC 83.82%), highlighting the potential of unsupervised learning to further improve accuracy.

By leveraging contrastive learning, unlabelled seismic data can be effectively utilised, reducing reliance on labelled datasets and enhancing model

generalisation. This suggests that contrastive learning remains a promising direction for improving shallow gas prediction, particularly in scenarios where labelled data is scarce.

In contrast, ResNet34 model generally underperformed, likely due to its larger parameter count, making it more prone to overfitting on the limited dataset. Additionally, models trained without augmentation or threshold optimisation exhibited lower recall, suggesting it failed to generalise well to varied seismic image conditions. The object detection model performed well at finding the heights of the gas regions, however the localisation accuracy depended heavily on the size and position of the bounding box on the image. Segmentation models showed mixed results, as predicting exact gas boundaries remains challenging due to image noise and feature overlap.

The segmentation results show that the PSPNet demonstrated the best performance among the evaluated models, with the highest Dice score (77.03%), IoU (62.64%), and accuracy (99.53%). Its Pyramid Pooling Module, which captures multi-scale contextual information, was particularly effective in identifying complex spatial structures, making it well-suited for segmenting shallow gas regions in seismic data.

Substantively, these results highlight the feasibility of deep learning in automating shallow gas detection, potentially reducing reliance on manual interpretation and improving the efficiency of geological risk assessment. Furthermore, the consistent success of EfficientNet across multiple tasks reinforces its effectiveness as a robust and efficient backbone for seismic image analysis, offering both computational efficiency and high predictive power.

While our results demonstrate the potential of deep learning in detecting shallow gas, several limitations must be considered. First, the labelled images used in this study were annotated by a domain expert. Human annotation is inherently subjective, and details might have been missed or misinterpreted due to image noise, artefacts, or paper damage of the records. These inconsistencies in the ground truth could influence the models' learning process, especially when training on a limited dataset where small errors in labelling may amplify as the model learns to generalise.

Another limitation comes from the structure of our pipeline, which relies on the output of one model to inform the next. This interdependence means that errors from earlier stages in the pipeline can propagate and negatively affect subsequent

tasks. Additionally, the naive tiling strategy employed in our approach introduces potential drawbacks as it limits the model’s ability to capture the complete context of a gas pocket. By cropping the seismic images into smaller tiles, there is a risk of missing important features, especially if gas pockets extend across multiple tiles. Lastly, the limited data size and data imbalance presented large challenges for modelling and shallow gas prediction. A greater quantity of labelled data should improve model training. Even higher amounts of unlabelled data can give more power for self-supervised learning strategies such as contrastive learning.

8 Future Work

8.1 Data preprocessing

Image processing results indicate that procedural and parametric choices in image preprocessing significantly influence image similarity and noise characteristics. However, the parameter selection process relied on heuristic visual assessment rather than a formal optimisation framework. Future work should focus on developing a systematic, data-driven approach to parameter tuning, ensuring that selections maximise waveform clarity while minimising noise amplification. One avenue for further research is the implementation of ML-based parametric optimisation. An automated optimisation framework could iteratively refine processing parameters using similarity metrics as objective functions, enabling a more rigorous evaluation of the trade-offs between noise suppression and structural fidelity. However, as image similarity does not necessarily correlate with improved ML performance, it is essential to compare optimised preprocessing parameters against ML model accuracy in downstream tasks such as feature classification and geological boundary delineation.

8.2 Detecting handwritten labels

For label detection, we applied EasyOCR on a single image and derived the conclusion that the original image has better OCR performance than pre-processed images. Due to the varying quality of the images, this conclusion might not hold in general across a wider dataset. More quantitative investigations should be performed across the range of available OCR tools and images in future work. Identifying the vertical lines and slicing the image into sections (as shown in Section 6.2) before performing OCR may also be beneficial for performance.

8.3 Shallow gas detection

To improve gas detection, there are numerous avenues to explore for refining the image preprocessing pipeline, particularly the tiling strategy. One potential avenue is the use of overlapping tiles, which could help ensure that features across tile boundaries are captured more effectively. Different cropping ratios may also minimise the loss of spatial information. Alternatively, adopting multi-scale architectures could allow the model to better handle varying spatial resolutions and mitigate the information loss associated with image resizing. This may improve the model's ability to detect smaller, more subtle features.

Future research could explore the use of hybrid deep learning approaches, combining both supervised and unsupervised learning techniques. Contrastive learning, for example, has shown promise in improving model robustness, and further refinement of this approach could allow for more effective use of unlabelled seismic data. Leveraging unsupervised learning could help create models that are less reliant on manual annotations, making them more adaptable to new and unseen images. There is also the potential to automatically extract information from the summary cards that come paired with some of the records, which may be useful metadata for further analysis. In addition, the models in the workflow need to be optimised and put into an automatic pipeline.

9 Conclusion

The aim of the DSG was to extract information from images of paper seismic records. Three research questions were tackled: effective preprocessing of the images, extraction of handwritten labels, and detecting shallow gas. The data for this study group were heterogeneous with challenges to overcome including differing image sizes, lack of contrast between background and foreground, and damage to the original paper records.

During this DSG, clear progress was made in utilising legacy seismic records. The image preprocessing research has shown that visual improvements in clarity can be made by combining multiple image processing techniques. These techniques can be tailored to each image, and most steps have been shown to have limited effect on similarity metrics indicating that the structure of the images have not changed, but the clarity is improved. These techniques have made visual improvements but more importantly, have improved the results in the shallow gas detection task,

indicating the power of image enhancement before applying ML techniques.

The second area of exploration was whether labelling within the images could be automatically extracted to align the survey records in space. Vertical spacing lines that indicate points of known survey vessel location have been accurately identified within images, which allows for the images to be georeferenced and aligned in space. OCR investigations have shown that EasyOCR has some success in identifying handwritten labels annotating the vertical lines, particularly whether an image subsection contains text or not. However, the varied accuracy of the found text means that the current results cannot be relied upon. Further investigations of post-processing of the OCR results could improve the detection accuracy by manipulating the returned output into the format of the labels. Automation of geographical alignment is an important step to enable efficient use of legacy seismic records.

This study developed an integrated ML framework for shallow gas detection from legacy seismogram scans, incorporating image processing and waveform enhancement alongside classification and object detection. Classification confidence scores refined object detection, which in turn improved data balance for segmentation, strengthening feature identification. The application of modern deep learning techniques to legacy seismic data demonstrated the feasibility of automated feature extraction in complex geophysical datasets. Preprocessing contributed to an improvement in model evaluation metrics, highlighting the impact of data conditioning on ML performance. The challenge questions were addressed by developing a structured methodology for gas detection, validating deep learning-based seismic interpretation, and quantifying the effects of preprocessing on model accuracy. These results establish a foundation for further refinement and extension of ML approaches in seismic analysis.

10 Team members

Moronfoluwa Akintola is an MSc Data Science graduate from the University of Hertfordshire. He created an evaluation dataset by manually classifying preprocessed image slices into “text” and “no text” categories, establishing a reliable ground truth for analysis. He also applied advanced image preprocessing techniques and evaluated the performance of OCR models.

Javier Alfaro is a Master of Geographic Data Science graduate from London

School of Economics and Political Science. His research interests lie at the intersection of GeoAI and deep learning, with a focus on urban analytics, spatial modelling, and remote sensing. He was co-facilitator of this project and contributed on initial georeferencing efforts, alongside modelling for classification, segmentation and combined workflow.

Jocelyn Japnanto is a 1st-year PhD researcher at University College London (UCL) with a focus on machine learning applications in seismology. She has a background in physics and medical physics. She contributed to the development of classification models for gas detection and some preliminary automated cropping techniques.

Ziwen Lu is a Master of Public Policy (STEM) graduate from Georgetown University. Her contributions to this project include applying wavelet-based denoising techniques to image processing, analysing and visualising key image quality parameters such as SSIM, PSNR, IoU, and Dice scores. Additionally, she reported the findings to the Alan Turing Institute and contributed to the corresponding sections of this report.

Eric Martin is a Lecturer of Civil Environmental Engineering at University of Greenwich, specialised in background in gas transport in porous media, and has previously lectured at Queen's University and The University of Birmingham as well as acting as a subject matter expert with the Ontario Ministry of the Environment. He was a co-facilitator of this project, and led implementation of the image processing method employed, and wrote the corresponding theory sections of this report.

Mukharbek Organokov is a PhD in Astrophysics and a machine learning engineer at Cisco. He proposed the architecture of a three-step pipeline for enhanced gas detection. He also contributed to segmentation models that use the output data from object detection models.

Julia Patsiukova is a PhD researcher at the University of Westminster with an MSc in Applied Informatics and Data Science. She also has a strong interest in bioinformatics, focusing on oncogenetics and leveraging computational tools to enhance gene therapy by optimizing ASO design and targeting strategies for improved therapeutic outcomes.

Mozhdeh Shiranirad is a postdoctoral research fellow at the University of Southampton working on the application of AI in healthcare data. She has a background in mathematics and machine learning.

Reem Tohme is a MSc Applied Social Data Science student at the London School of Economics and Political Science. She contributed to image wrangling for the OCR extraction of handwritten labels, crucial for the future geomapping of shallow gas. She compared the behaviour of different image versions with EasyOCR.

Linfeng Wang is a PhD student at the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, specializing in bioinformatics and machine learning for pathogen genomics. In this work, he generated datasets tailored to a range of image recognition tasks from raw data. He developed and fine-tuned image classification models, implemented contrastive learning to leverage unlabelled data, and designed an object detection modelling method. Additionally, he benchmarked classification performance across varying image preprocessing parameters and initiated exploratory work in image segmentation.

Kathryn Leeming is a data scientist at the British Geological Survey. Her role in this project was PI: constructing the data challenge from the questions of interest, discussing the ongoing work, and editing the report.

Kingsley Ezenwaka is a marine geoscientist at the British Geological Survey. He prepared data for the DSG and was the Challenge Owner, explaining the scientific context of this work and consulting on seismic questions.

References

- [1] ABID, B., KHAN, B. M., AND MEMON, R. A. Seismic facies segmentation using ensemble of convolutional neural networks. *Wireless communications and mobile computing* 2022, 1 (2022), 7762543.
- [2] BELVAL, E., DELTEIL, T., SCHADE, M., AND RADHAKRISHNA, S. Amazon Textractor. <https://github.com/aws-samples/amazon-textract-textractor>, 2024. (accessed: 29/01/2025).
- [3] BODAPATI, J. D., SAJJA, R., AND NARALASETTI, V. An efficient approach for semantic segmentation of salt domes in seismic images using improved unet architecture. *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series B* 104, 3 (2023), 569–578.
- [4] BRADSKI, G. The OpenCV Library. *Dr. Dobb's Journal of Software Tools* (2000).

- [5] CANNY, J. A computational approach to edge detection. *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 6 (1986), 679–698.
- [6] CARLSON, J., BRYAN, T., AND DELL, M. Efficient OCR for building a diverse digital history. In *Proceedings of the 62nd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)* (2024), pp. 8105–8115.
- [7] CHAPELLE, O., SCHÖLKOPF, B., AND ZIEN, A. *Semi-Supervised learning*. MIT Press, London, England, 2006.
- [8] CHEN, T., KORNBLITH, S., NOROUZI, M., AND HINTON, G. A simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations. In *International conference on machine learning* (2020), Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, pp. 1597–1607.
- [9] CIPRIANO, C., JUNIOR, D., DINIZ, P., MARIN, L., PAIVA, A., DINIZ, J., AND SILVA, A. Detection and delimitation of natural gas in seismic images using MLP-mixer and U-Net. In *Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems - Volume 2: ICEIS*, (2022), INSTICC, SciTePress, pp. 578–585.
- [10] CIPRIANO, C. L., JÚNIOR, D. A. D., DINIZ, P. S., MARIN, L. F., DE PAIVA, A. C., DINIZ, J. O. B., AND SILVA, A. C. Detection and delimitation of natural gas in seismic images using MLP-mixer and U-net. In *ICEIS (1)* (2022), pp. 578–585.
- [11] COOKE, R., BULAT, J., AND CHRISTIE, G. Marine geophysical data: digital capture of paper records. Tech. Rep. IR/10/078, British Geological Survey, 2012.
- [12] DU, Y., LI, C., GUO, R., CUI, C., LIU, W., ZHOU, J., LU, B., YANG, Y., LIU, Q., HU, X., YU, D., AND MA, Y. PP-OCRv2: Bag of tricks for ultra lightweight OCR system. *arXiv abs/2109.03144* (2021).
- [13] FAUSTOMORALES. keras-ocr 0.8.4. <https://github.com/faustomorales/keras-ocr>. (accessed: 29/01/2025).
- [14] FISHER, R. B., ET AL. Hough transform - HIPR2. <https://homepages.inf.ed.ac.uk/rbf/HIPR2/hough.htm>, 2024. (accessed: 05/02/2025).

- [15] FRANCIS, S., AND SANGEETHA, M. A comparison study on optical character recognition models in mathematical equations and in any language. *Results in Control and Optimization* 18 (2025), 100532.
- [16] FU, Z., KONG, Y., ZHENG, Y., YE, H., HU, W., YANG, J., AND HE, L. Cascaded detail-preserving networks for super-resolution of document images. *2019 International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR)* (2019), 240–245.
- [17] GONZALEZ, R. C., AND WOODS, R. E. *Digital Image Processing*, 3rd ed. Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ, 2008.
- [18] H. Python tesseract 0.3.13. <https://github.com/h/pytesseract>. (accessed: 28/01/2025).
- [19] HE, K., ZHANG, X., REN, S., AND SUN, J. Deep residual learning for image recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (2016), pp. 770–778.
- [20] HEGGHAMMER, T. OCR with Tesseract, Amazon Textract, and Google Document AI: A benchmarking experiment. *Journal of Computational Social Science* 5 (2022), 861–882.
- [21] HUANG, G., LIU, Z., VAN DER MAATEN, L., AND WEINBERGER, K. Q. Densely connected convolutional networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (2017), pp. 4700–4708.
- [22] IAKUBOVSKII, P. Segmentation models PyTorch. https://github.com/qubvel/segmentation_models.pytorch, 2019. (accessed: 29/01/2025).
- [23] JACCARD, P. Étude comparative de la distribution florale dans une portion du jura. *Bulletin of the New York Mathematical Society* 8 (1901), 1–30.
- [24] JAIDEDAI. EasyOCR 1.7.2. <https://github.com/JaidedAI/EasyOCR>. (accessed: 28/01/2025).
- [25] JAIN, P. H., KUMAR, V., SAMUEL, J., SINGH, S., MANNEPALLI, A., AND ANDERSON, R. Artificially intelligent readers: An adaptive framework for original handwritten numerical digits recognition with OCR methods. *Information* 14, 6 (2023), 305.

- [26] LEE, G. R., GOMMERS, R., WASILEWSKI, F., WOHLFAHRT, K., AND O’LEARY, A. PyWavelets: A python package for wavelet analysis. *Journal of Open Source Software* 4, 36 (2019), 1237.
- [27] LIN, T. Focal loss for dense object detection. *arXiv abs/1708.02002* (2017).
- [28] LIN, T.-Y., DOLLÁR, P., GIRSHICK, R., HE, K., HARIHARAN, B., AND BELONGIE, S. Feature pyramid networks for object detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (2017), pp. 2117–2125.
- [29] MILOSAVLJEVIĆ, A. Identification of salt deposits on seismic images using deep learning method for semantic segmentation. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* 9, 1 (2020), 24.
- [30] MOUGAN, C., PLANT, R., TENG, C., BAZZI, M., EGEA, A. C., CHAN, R. S., JASIN, D. S., STOFFEL, M., WHITAKER, K. J., AND MANSER, J. How to data in datathons. In *NeurIPS* (2023).
- [31] OTSU, N. A threshold selection method from gray-level histograms. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics* 9, 1 (1979), 62–66.
- [32] PIZER, S. M., AMBURN, E. P., AUSTIN, J. D., CROMARTIE, R., GESELOWITZ, A., GREER, T., TER HAAR ROMNEY, B., ZIMMERMAN, J. B., AND ZUIDERVELD, K. Adaptive histogram equalization and its variations. *Computer Vision, Graphics, and Image Processing* 39 (1987), 355–368.
- [33] QI, Y., HUANG, W. R., LI, Q., AND DEGANGE, J. DeepErase: Weakly supervised ink artifact removal in document text images. *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV)* (March 2020).
- [34] RONNEBERGER, O., FISCHER, P., AND BROX, T. U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation. In *Medical image computing and computer-assisted intervention—MICCAI 2015: 18th international conference, Munich, Germany, October 5-9, 2015, proceedings, part III 18* (2015), Springer, pp. 234–241.
- [35] SANDLER, M., HOWARD, A., ZHU, M., ZHMOGINOV, A., AND CHEN, L.-C. Mobilenetv2: Inverted residuals and linear bottlenecks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (2018), pp. 4510–4520.

- [36] SOBEL, I., AND FELDMAN, G. A 3x3 isotropic gradient operator for image processing. *Pattern Recognition and Image Analysis* (1968), 271–274.
- [37] SRIVASTAVA, N., HINTON, G., KRIZHEVSKY, A., SUTSKEVER, I., AND SALAKHUTDINOV, R. Dropout: A simple way to prevent neural networks from overfitting. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 15, 56 (2014), 1929–1958.
- [38] SUDRE, C. H., LI, W., VERCAUTEREN, T., OURSELIN, S., AND JORGE CARDOSO, M. Generalised dice overlap as a deep learning loss function for highly unbalanced segmentations. In *Deep Learning in Medical Image Analysis and Multimodal Learning for Clinical Decision Support: Third International Workshop, DLMIA 2017, and 7th International Workshop, ML-CDS 2017, Held in Conjunction with MICCAI 2017, Québec City, QC, Canada, September 14, Proceedings 3* (2017), Springer, pp. 240–248.
- [39] SØRENSEN, C. S. A method of measuring the intensity of echoes from echo sounders. *Hafnia I* (1945), 1–13.
- [40] TAN, M., AND LE, Q. Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks. In *International conference on machine learning* (2019), Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, pp. 6105–6114.
- [41] TOLSTIKHIN, I. O., HOULSBY, N., KOLESNIKOV, A., BEYER, L., ZHAI, X., UNTERTHINER, T., YUNG, J., STEINER, A., KEYSERS, D., USZKOREIT, J., ET AL. MLP-mixer: An all-MLP architecture for vision. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 34 (2021), 24261–24272.
- [42] VAN DER WALT, S., SCH ONBERGER, J. L., NUNEZ-IGLESIAS, J., BOULOGNE, F., WARNER, J. D., YAGER, N., GOUILLART, E., YU, T., AND THE SCIKIT-IMAGE CONTRIBUTORS. scikit-image: Image processing in python. *PeerJ* 2, e453 (2014).
- [43] VANSI, S. Comparison of text detection techniques: easyOCR vs kerasOCR vs paddleOCR vs pytesseract vs openCV. <https://medium.com/%40shah.vansh132/comparison-of-text-detection-techniques-easyocr-vs-kerasocr-vs-paddleocr-vs-2024>. accessed: 28/02/2025.
- [44] VEDHAVIYASSH, D., SUDHAN, R., SARANYA, G., SAFA, M., AND ARUN, D. Comparative analysis of easyOCR and tesseractOCR for automatic license plate recognition using deep learning algorithm. In *2022 6th International*

Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (2022), pp. 966–971.

- [45] WANG, Z., BOVIK, A. C., SHEIKH, H. R., AND SIMONCELLI, E. P. Image quality assessment: From error visibility to structural similarity. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing* 13, 4 (2004), 600–612.
- [46] WANG, Z., WANG, Q., YANG, Y., LIU, N., CHEN, Y., AND GAO, J. Seismic facies segmentation via a segformer-based specific encoder–decoder–hypercolumns scheme. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 61 (2023), 1–11.
- [47] XIE, E., WANG, W., YU, Z., ANANDKUMAR, A., ALVAREZ, J. M., AND LUO, P. Segformer: Simple and efficient design for semantic segmentation with transformers. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 34 (2021), 12077–12090.
- [48] YANG, Y., ZHANG, L., DU, M., BO, J., LIU, H., REN, L., LI, X., AND DEEN, M. J. A comparative analysis of eleven neural networks architectures for small datasets of lung images of COVID-19 patients toward improved clinical decisions. *Computers in Biology and Medicine* 139 (2021), 104887.
- [49] ZHAO, H., SHI, J., QI, X., WANG, X., AND JIA, J. Pyramid scene parsing network. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* (2017), pp. 2881–2890.
- [50] ZINI, J. E., RIZK, Y., AND AWAD, M. A deep transfer learning framework for seismic data analysis: A case study on bright spot detection. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing* 58 (2020), 3202–3212.

Appendix

A Image Similarity Metrics

Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) - Pre-Thresholding

The Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) is a metric designed to assess the perceptual similarity between two images. Unlike pixel-wise metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE) or Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), SSIM evaluates similarity based on structural information, luminance, and contrast. It is defined for greyscale images as [45]:

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + C_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + C_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2)}$$

where μ_x and μ_y are the mean intensities, σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 are the variances, and σ_{xy} represents the covariance between the original image x and the processed image y . Constants C_1 and C_2 stabilise the calculation when the denominators approach zero.

In the context of image-enhanced seismic reflection scans, SSIM is useful for quantifying the preservation of structural features such as reflectors, fault lines, and stratigraphic boundaries. SSIM values range from 0 to 1, where a value closer to 1 indicates higher similarity between the images, and higher values are desirable for preserving structural features.

In this study, SSIM was calculated after each processing step, prior to the application of thresholding. Post-thresholding, SSIM was no longer a meaningful metric due to the binary nature of the images, which eliminates the continuous intensity variations required for SSIM to effectively assess structural similarity.

Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) - Pre-Thresholding

The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) is a metric used to evaluate the quality of an image by comparing it to a reference image [17]. PSNR is derived from the Mean Squared Error (MSE) and quantifies the ratio between the maximum possible pixel intensity and the level of noise introduced by processing. It is defined as:

$$PSNR = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{MAX_I^2}{MSE} \right)$$

where MAX_I represents the maximum saturation value of the image (e.g., 255 for 8-bit images), and MSE is the mean squared error between the original and processed images.

PSNR provides an objective measure of the fidelity of processed images, indicating how much noise or distortion has been introduced during enhancement procedures. Higher PSNR values indicate lower levels of distortion relative to the original image. Generally, PSNR values above 30 dB correspond to high-quality images with minimal visible noise, while values in the 20–30 dB range indicate moderate noise levels that may introduce noticeable artifacts. PSNR values below 20 dB suggest significant noise or distortion, often degrading perceptual image quality [17].

In this study, PSNR was calculated after each processing step, prior to thresholding. Post-thresholding, PSNR was not applicable due to the binary nature of the images, which reduces pixel intensity variance, rendering the metric ineffective for meaningful quality assessment.

Edge Preservation Index (EPI) - Pre-Thresholding

The Edge Preservation Index (EPI) [17] is a metric used to quantify the extent to which image processing techniques maintain the integrity of edge features. EPI is calculated by applying an edge detection operator, such as the Sobel filter [36], to both the original and processed images and then computing the correlation between the resulting edge maps. It is defined as:

$$EPI = \text{corr}(S(x), S(y))$$

where $S(x)$ and $S(y)$ represent the Sobel edge-detected versions of the original image x and the processed image y , respectively. The correlation coefficient measures the linear relationship between the two edge maps, with values ranging from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates perfect edge preservation.

EPI was used to provide a metric for assessing whether processing steps preserved geological features represented by sharp discontinuities. High EPI values indicate strong preservation of these structural edges. EPI was calculated after each processing step to monitor the impact of enhancement techniques on edge features prior to thresholding.

Intersection over Union (IoU) - Post-Thresholding

The Intersection over Union (IoU), or Jaccard Index [23], was used to evaluate the similarity between two binary images by comparing the overlap of their foreground

regions. IoU is defined as the ratio of the intersection to the union of the binary masks:

$$IoU = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}$$

where A and B represent the sets of foreground pixels in the original and processed binary images, respectively. The numerator quantifies the number of overlapping pixels, while the denominator accounts for the total number of unique foreground pixels present in either image. IoU values range from 0 to 1, with 1 indicating perfect overlap.

IoU was used to assess the consistency of binary features and provides a quantitative measure of how well the thresholded image retained the structural features present in the original or reference binary mask. IoU was calculated post-thresholding to evaluate the degree of overlap between the binarised processed image and the corresponding reference binary mask, providing insight into the effectiveness of the thresholding and enhancement techniques in preserving key structural features.

Dice Coefficient - Post-Thresholding

The Dice Coefficient, or Sørensen–Dice Index [39], was used to quantify the similarity between two binary images. It measures the overlap between the foreground regions of the images:

$$Dice = \frac{2|A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|}$$

where A and B represent the sets of foreground pixels in the original and processed binary images, respectively. The numerator reflects twice the number of overlapping pixels, while the denominator is the sum of the foreground pixels in both images. Dice values range from 0 to 1, with 1 indicating perfect similarity.

The Dice Coefficient was used to assess the consistency of binary features, such as reflector boundaries and gridlines, following thresholding. It is particularly sensitive to differences in small structures, making it effective for evaluating the preservation of fine details. It was calculated post-thresholding to compare the binarised processed image with the corresponding reference binary mask, providing a complementary measure to IoU for evaluating the accuracy of structural feature retention.

B Evaluation Metrics for Deep Learning

To assess the performance of our models across classification, object detection, and segmentation tasks, multiple evaluation metrics were employed.

Classification Metrics

For the classification models, we calculated the following metrics:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

$$\text{AUC-ROC} = \int_0^1 TPR(FPR) d(FPR)$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

Where:

- TP (True Positives): correctly identified gas-bearing tiles
- TN (True Negatives): correctly identified non-gas tiles
- FP (False Positives): non-gas tiles incorrectly classified as gas
- FN (False Negatives): gas-bearing tiles missed by the model
- TPR (True positive rate): $TP/(TP + FN)$
- FPR (False positive rate): $FP/(FP + TN)$

Object Detection Metrics

For object detection, we introduced the following metrics:

$$\text{Mean Intersection over Union (mIoU)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{A_i \cap B_i}{A_i \cup B_i} \quad (2)$$

Where A_i is the predicted bounding box and B_i is the ground truth box for the i -th sample. N represents the total number of samples.

$$\text{Mean Center Distance Error (MCDE)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{(x_i^{pred} - x_i^{gt})^2 + (y_i^{pred} - y_i^{gt})^2} \quad (3)$$

Where (x_i^{pred}, y_i^{pred}) are the coordinates of the predicted box centre, and (x_i^{gt}, y_i^{gt}) are the coordinates of the ground truth centre.

$$\text{Mean Width Error (MWE)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |w_i^{pred} - w_i^{gt}| \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Mean Height Error (MHE)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |h_i^{pred} - h_i^{gt}| \quad (5)$$

Where w_i and h_i represent the width and height of the predicted and ground truth bounding boxes, respectively.

Segmentation Metrics

For segmentation tasks, in addition to accuracy, sensitivity, and AUC-ROC, the following metrics were also evaluated:

$$\text{IoU (Jaccard Index)} = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Dice Coefficient} = \frac{2|A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|} \quad (7)$$

Where A is the predicted mask and B is the ground truth mask.

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